

Alcohol Consumption as a Degenerating Factor to Gender-based Violence in South Africa

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Gender-based violence (GBV) continues to be a widespread and deeply rooted issue in South Africa. Among the key contributing factors, alcohol consumption has been identified as a significant driver, intensifying aggression and increasing the likelihood of violent behaviour. This study investigates the role of alcohol in perpetuating GBV against women, employing a qualitative approach through secondary data analysis. The research aims to explore the relationship between alcohol use and the incidence of GBV, identify contributing factors, and assess the impact of alcohol-related violence on the well-being of affected women. The findings reveal a strong correlation between alcohol consumption and GBV, with contributing factors including poverty, lack of economic independence, and entrenched traditional gender norms. Victims often endure long-term physical, psychological, emotional, and behavioural consequences as a result of the violence. To address these challenges and promote safer communities, the study recommends a multifaceted approach: re-evaluating harmful cultural norms, enforcing alcohol-related legislation, increasing community engagement and awareness, regulating alcohol availability, and enhancing support services for both victims and perpetrators.

Keywords: Alcohol, gender-based violence, women

South African President Cyril Ramaphosa has repeatedly spoken out against Gender-Based Violence (GBV), describing it as a “national crisis” and referring to it as the “second pandemic” following COVID-19. During the State of the Nation Address (2020), President Ramaphosa stated that “*Violence against women and children has become more than a national crisis; it is a deep stain on our conscience. We must act urgently and decisively to end this scourge.*” He also acknowledged that alcohol abuse significantly contributes to GBV, as many violent incidents are perpetrated by intoxicated individuals. In response, the President introduced stricter regulations on alcohol sales and advocated for harsher penalties for those convicted of GBV (Netshitangani, 2021).

GBV is not only a pressing issue in South Africa but also a global concern. Both the United Nations (UN) and the World Health Organization (WHO) have noted that alcohol abuse increases the likelihood of domestic violence (WHO, 2021). According to Graham, Bernards, Wilsnack, and Gmel (2011) indicates that a substantial proportion of domestic violence incidents occur when the perpetrator is under the influence of alcohol. Nations like Canada and Australia have implemented stringent alcohol control measures aimed at reducing alcohol-related violence (Enaifoghe, Dlelana, Durokifa, & Dlamini, 2021). In addition, several countries have developed integrated programs targeting both substance abuse and support for GBV victims, highlighting the need for a multifaceted

approach.

One of the most high-profile GBV cases in South Africa was the 2019 murder of Uyinene Mrwetyana, a 19-year-old university student. Although her tragic case was not directly linked to alcohol, it sparked nationwide protests and brought renewed attention to the GBV crisis. In contrast, many other GBV cases in the country are closely tied to alcohol abuse. For instance, in the same year, a woman in Johannesburg was fatally assaulted by her partner following heavy drinking (Amakoh, 2023).

To address the GBV crisis, the South African government has launched several initiatives and legal reforms. In 2020, the National Strategic Plan on Gender-Based Violence and Femicide (2020-2030) was introduced, aiming to prevent GBV, provide support to survivors, and ensure accountability for offenders (National Strategic Plan on Gender-Based Violence & Femicide, 2020). Additionally, President Ramaphosa unveiled the Emergency Response Action Plan on GBV, which prioritises increased funding for GBV-related programs, improved police responsiveness, and a more effective justice system (Deane, 2024).

Despite these efforts, GBV continues to escalate, and one of the most pressing challenges is the lack of comprehensive interventions that address both alcohol abuse and GBV concurrently. As such, this study seeks to examine the role of alcohol consumption in perpetuating gender-based violence against women in South Africa.

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Review of Literature

Gender-based violence (GBV) remains a pervasive public health and human rights issue globally, with alcohol consumption consistently identified as a major contributing factor in both the initiation and escalation of violent behaviour, particularly in intimate relationships. Numerous studies across various contexts have established a strong correlation between alcohol abuse and the perpetration of GBV. Research conducted in the United States and the United Kingdom found that a significant proportion of GBV incidents occurred when perpetrators were intoxicated (Cook,

Wilson, & Thomas, 2018). These findings highlight a pattern that transcends national borders, suggesting a global trend where alcohol impairs judgment, reduces inhibitions, and increases aggression, all of which can trigger or worsen violent behaviour. The World Health Organisation (2021) reinforces this connection, reporting that individuals who engage in heavy and frequent drinking are at a significantly greater risk of becoming both perpetrators and victims of violence. Alcohol serves as a situational catalyst that exacerbates underlying tensions, conflicts, or power imbalances within intimate relationships (Rodriguez, Neighbors, & Knee, 2014).

In South Africa, alcohol-related GBV is particularly widespread, cutting across urban and rural settings and affecting individuals from all socioeconomic backgrounds (Govera, 2021). Cultural and historical associations between alcohol, masculinity, and social bonding often normalise heavy drinking among men, which in turn contributes to increased aggression in domestic settings (Sebeelo, 2021).

Shiva, Shukla, and Chandra (2021) emphasise the dual role of alcohol in the South African GBV context, as both a perpetration factor and a coping mechanism for victims. Their study shows that alcohol consumption amplifies violent tendencies, especially in relationships already strained by conflict or inequality. In addition, victims, particularly women, may turn to alcohol as a means of self-medicating trauma, thereby increasing their vulnerability to further abuse.

Mtotywa and Ledwaba (2023) note that alcohol acts as a direct trigger for violent behaviour due to its impact on the brain's ability to regulate impulse and emotion. High levels of alcohol consumption significantly increase the likelihood of GBV, often escalating minor disagreements into physical confrontations.

Socio-economic and Structural Factors

Economic stressors such as unemployment, poverty, and housing instability also play a critical role in linking alcohol consumption with GBV. Mesfin (2013) argues that in communities under economic strain, alcohol is frequently used as an escape from daily hardships, which can lead to higher levels of domestic violence. This creates a vicious cycle where alcohol use worsens household conditions, increases stress, and leads to repeated incidents of violence.

Furthermore, limited awareness and education around the harmful effects of alcohol and its connection to violence contribute to the normalisation of GBV. According to Salmon (2019), the acceptance of alcohol consumption in marginalised communities often leads to delayed or non-existent responses to abuse, discouraging victims from seeking justice or help.

Policy and Prevention Efforts

While alcohol control policies such as reducing alcohol outlet density, limiting sales hours, and raising the legal drinking age have shown some promise in lowering GBV rates, their effectiveness varies by context (Shiva et al., 2021). South Africa's temporary alcohol bans during the COVID-19 lockdowns led to a notable decline in intimate partner homicides, underscoring the potential impact of alcohol regulation on violence prevention (Brodie, 2020).

Nevertheless, policy responses must be part of a broader, multi-sectoral approach that addresses the root causes of GBV, including patriarchal norms, poverty, and systemic inequality. Effective interventions should include community education, support services

for victims, substance abuse treatment programs, and efforts to transform harmful gender norms.

Relevance of the Study

South Africa faced ongoing challenges related to alcohol consumption and its connection to Gender-Based Violence (GBV). This study aimed to raise awareness among community members, policymakers, and stakeholders about how alcohol contributed to the escalation of GBV. By shedding light on these dynamics, the research sought to deepen understanding of the issue and its impact on community well-being. The study examined cultural norms, societal attitudes, and individual behaviours influenced by alcohol that contributed to GBV in the South African context. Through this exploration, it informed the development of targeted interventions and prevention strategies. These insights were considered crucial for creating effective programs aimed at reducing alcohol-related GBV and promoting healthier, more respectful relationships within communities.

In addition, the research aimed to strengthen support systems for survivors of GBV in South Africa. Its findings were used to challenge harmful social norms, advocate for policy reform, and promote the creation of safer environments where survivors could access the support services needed to heal and thrive. Ultimately, the study contributed to building more resilient communities across South Africa. Addressing the underlying drivers of GBV linked to alcohol use and advocating for systemic changes helps protect women from the harmful effects of alcohol-related violence. This led to improved community well-being, greater social cohesion, and enhanced safety for all.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the relationship between alcohol consumption and the incidence of GBV in South Africa.
- To identify factors that contribute to alcohol-related GBV in South Africa.
- To assess the impact of alcohol-related GBV on the well-being of women in South Africa.

Method

This study employed a qualitative research approach and analytic research design to gain a comprehensive understanding of the role of alcohol consumption in gender-based violence (GBV) against women in South Africa. This study relied on secondary data, which was gathered from journal articles, government reports, publications from non-governmental organisations (NGOs), policy briefs and credible media reports. The inclusion criteria focused on sources written in English, published within the last five years, and directly related to issues of GBV and alcohol consumption in the South African context. The thematic content analysis approach was used to analyse the data.

Results and Discussion

The Relationship between Alcohol Consumption and the Incidence of GBV in South Africa

According to Machisa (2021), there is substantial evidence indicating a strong link between alcohol consumption and gender-based violence (GBV). The study found that men who frequently consume alcohol significantly increase the likelihood of

perpetrating GBV, while women whose partners regularly drink are up to six times more likely to experience violence. Similarly, Brodie (2020) observed a notable decline in intimate partner homicides during the COVID-19 alcohol bans, suggesting a direct causal relationship between alcohol availability and GBV rates. This indicates that reduced alcohol consumption can lead to a measurable decrease in fatal GBV incidents.

The World Health Organisation (WHO, 2021) also highlighted that individuals who drink heavily and frequently are at a higher risk of becoming both victims and perpetrators of violence. Supporting this, Parrott, Leone, Schipani-McLaughlin, Salazar, Nizam, and Gilmore (2023) reported that between 34% and 74% of sexual assault offenders were under the influence of alcohol at the time of the offence, and that approximately 50% of sexual assault cases involve alcohol use by either or both parties. Furthermore, Shiva et al. (2021) noted that the use of additional substances such as cannabis and stimulants alongside alcohol has an additive effect, further escalating the risk of GBV. These findings provide overwhelming evidence that alcohol serves as both a direct and indirect contributor to GBV in South Africa. It acts as a catalyst, intensifying existing risk factors at individual, relational, and societal levels.

Factors that Contribute to Alcohol-related GBV

Culture and Tradition: Nduna (2021) observed that, culturally, men in South Africa are often positioned in dominant roles over women due to longstanding customs such as lobola (bride price) and traditional male circumcision. These practices frequently reinforce the perception that women occupy an inherently subordinate status. Over time, such norms become deeply ingrained, with both men and women socialised to accept and uphold these cultural and religious customs. Unfortunately, some of these traditions, whether implicitly or explicitly, condone or normalise gender-based violence (GBV).

Economic Dependency: Cameron and Tedds (2021) argued that the lack of economic independence among women significantly contributes to GBV. Financial dependency often prevents women from leaving abusive relationships. Their research highlighted a strong correlation between poverty and GBV. However, Daniel (2023) cautioned against viewing poverty as the sole driver of GBV. Instead, he contended that economic stress often becomes a mechanism for reasserting male dominance and authority. Women's access to education and employment challenges traditional gender roles, leading some men to feel emasculated. In response, violence is sometimes used as a means to reassert control (Cameron & Tedds, 2021).

Mental Stability: Machisa (2021) further identified childhood trauma, mental health challenges, substance abuse, and poor communication or conflict resolution skills within relationships as key drivers of GBV. Ironically, these factors are frequently both caused by and intensified through alcohol misuse, untreated mental health issues, and early exposure to abuse. In the South African context, distorted constructions of masculinity, economic hardship, and entrenched gender power imbalances interact with alcohol consumption to significantly increase the risk and prevalence of GBV.

The Impact of Alcohol-related GBV on the Well-being of Women

Bdier and Mahamid (2021) found mounting evidence that gender-

based violence (GBV) has profound physical, psychological, emotional, and behavioral effects on women's health and well-being.

Physical Impact: Physically, victims may suffer head trauma (from hitting, punching, or stabbing), back pain (from kicking or falls), hearing loss, vision damage, internal organ injuries, cardiovascular issues, miscarriages, HIV infection, pregnancy complications, and brain disorders. These injuries often have long-term consequences, including vision loss and reduced mobility. Rizkalla, Alsamman, Bakr, Masud, Sbini, and Segal (2024) support these findings, noting that survivors frequently experience physical symptoms linked to depression, such as shoulder and back pain, and may engage in overeating, leading to obesity and worsening conditions like diabetes and arthritis. The negative effects are often intensified by socio-economic factors, such as limited access to healthcare.

Psychological Impact: Psychologically, survivors of GBV commonly suffer from posttraumatic stress disorder (e.g., intrusive memories & nightmares), major depressive disorder (e.g., emotional numbness, hopelessness, anger, appetite changes), generalized anxiety disorder, and complex trauma. These conditions can result in a persistent sense of emptiness, intense emotions, and a lack of internal control (Bdier & Mahamid, 2021). Melgar, Campdepadrós, Fuentes-Pumarola, & Mut-Montalvá, (2021) add that victims often struggle with self-worth, especially when the perpetrator is someone expected to nurture and protect them. This betrayal can lead to deep humiliation and emotional disorientation, whether the abuse is physical or verbal. Finally, Bdier and Mahamid (2021) highlight that many victims experience suicidal thoughts as a way to escape the abuse, often feeling worthless, isolated, fearful, and lacking in confidence.

Findings of the Study

- There is substantial evidence indicating a strong link between alcohol consumption and gender-based violence (GBV)
- Gender roles rooted in tradition (e.g., male dominance, lobola) normalize and justify GBV.
- Poverty and lack of economic independence trap women in abusive relationships.
- Shifting Gender Roles and Masculine Identity Crisis
- High unemployment, especially among young men, increases stress and insecurity, fuelling GBV.
- GBV has physical (back pains, head trauma), psychological (depression), emotional, and behavioural (violent behaviour) effects on women's health and well-being.

Conclusion

This study set out to examine the relationship between alcohol consumption and the incidence of gender-based violence (GBV) against women in South Africa. The findings show that alcohol consumption significantly contributes to the occurrence and severity of GBV. The findings of this study contribute new insights to the growing body of literature by highlighting the complex and interrelated nature of alcohol misuse, cultural norms, economic dependency, and psychological trauma in perpetuating GBV. However, the study is not without limitations. The use of secondary data imposes constraints on the depth of analysis and limits the ability to capture real-time or region-specific nuances. Moreover, generalizing findings to the entire country may overlook important differences in cultural practices, alcohol availability, and

enforcement of GBV laws across provinces. Future research should consider mixed-methods approaches that combine large-scale quantitative data with qualitative insights from affected communities, particularly in rural and underrepresented areas.

From a systemic perspective, the implications of these findings are far-reaching. Policy efforts must go beyond punitive legal approaches and include the implementation of comprehensive, evidence-based interventions. These should encompass stricter regulation of alcohol sales, increased availability of rehabilitation and support services for both victims and perpetrators. In conclusion, reducing alcohol-related GBV requires an integrated strategy that addresses the root causes of both alcohol misuse.

Recommendations

Reduce alcohol availability and promote responsible drinking. Alcohol consumption is a known risk factor for violent behaviour, including gender-based violence (GBV). Limiting access to alcohol and encouraging healthier drinking habits can significantly reduce alcohol-related GBV incidents. Strategies may include regulating sales, increasing taxation on alcoholic beverages, and running public health campaigns on the risks of excessive alcohol consumption.

Expand access to counselling and medical support for both victims and perpetrators. Both victims and perpetrators of alcohol-related GBV require access to specialised support services. Perpetrators, often men, may struggle with alcohol dependency and require professional help to address addiction and change violent behaviour. Simultaneously, victims, frequently women and children, need ongoing medical care, trauma counselling, and psychosocial support. Expanding access to services through government-funded rehabilitation centres, mobile health units in underserved areas, and confidential helplines is essential for recovery and prevention.

Strengthen community-based awareness and education campaigns. Comprehensive GBV awareness campaigns can play a critical role in reshaping public attitudes toward gender relations, alcohol use, and violence. Community engagement initiatives should focus on education, stigma reduction, and the promotion of respectful, non-violent relationships. These campaigns must be culturally sensitive and inclusive, using various platforms such as schools, media, and local gatherings.

Enforce alcohol regulations and strengthen GBV legislation. Effective enforcement of existing alcohol and GBV-related laws is crucial to reducing violence. Local governments should monitor and regulate alcohol outlet operating hours and licensing. At the same time, GBV laws must be applied consistently, with accountability mechanisms in place. Policies should be tailored to fit the local context and supported by broader societal efforts to change harmful norms.

Encourage cultural reflection and reform. Cultural practices and beliefs that normalise or excuse violence must be critically re-evaluated. Community leaders, educators, and religious figures should be involved in facilitating dialogue around cultural norms that contribute to GBV, promoting values of equality, respect, and non-violence.

Increase male involvement in GBV prevention efforts. Engaging men and boys in initiatives aimed at transforming harmful gender norms is vital. Programs should encourage positive masculinity, challenge stereotypes, and promote male responsibility in ending GBV. Male champions can be instrumental in leading change within their communities.

Limitations of the Study

One limitation of this study is its reliance on secondary data, which comes with inherent constraints. Additionally, the findings were generalised to the entire country, despite potential regional variations that may not have been adequately captured in the data.

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